

GALLERY: Caen Highland Township - 1813

From left to right: Outside of longhouse from Reconstruction; (top) HeritageAtHome about the Clearances; (bottom) whisky still from reconstruction; Sutherland chair – 3D

Gallery Content

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During the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries the inhabitants of many small farming communities in the Scottish Highlands were forced to leave their homes. Under the guise of improvement landlords drove out traditional subsistence farmers and created a much less densely occupied landscape. One of the communities affected by this process of 'clearance' was the township of Caen in Sutherland.

Caen was located in the lower part of the Strath of Kildonan. This area was cleared particularly brutally by representatives of the Duke of Sutherland between 1813 and 1819. Several families resisted the clearances and soldiers were sent from Fort George to maintain order. Today only a few foundations indicate where a thriving farming community [once stood](#).

Reconstructions

Caen Pre-Clearances – 1813 [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4475543](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4475543)

Image: Longhouse and farm buildings at Caen as they may have seemed in 1813 (Credit: Open Virtual Worlds).

This reconstruction shows the Caen township as it may have looked in 1813, just before the families who lived and worked here were forced out from the Strath of Kildonan.

There is a video preview of the reconstruction on [Vimeo](#).

A 360° tour of the reconstruction can be found on [RoundMe](#).

The full reconstruction can be downloaded for Windows devices [here](#).

The gallery also includes an [earlier digital representation](#) of Caen created in OpenSim, which was also exhibited at Timespan.

3D Objects

List of 3D objects currently published on Zenodo.

Sutherland Chair [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4406982](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4406982)

Associated Resources

A tour of the reconstruction and discussion of the Highland Clearances by Jacquie Aitken and Anne Coombs of the research behind it can be found [here](#).

A gallery of related media is available [here](#).

How Has the Gallery Been Used?

The reconstruction of Caen was featured in the [Real Rights](#) exhibition at [Timespan](#) in Helmsdale.

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Discover More

Information held by Historic Environment Scotland about pre-historic sites in and around Caen can be accessed via [Canmore](#). CANMORE

You can see how Helmsdale & its harbour look today on [Google Maps](#).

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This reconstruction was part of the [CINE](#) project for digital heritage in northern environments. The project received funding from the European Union's [Northern Periphery and Arctic Programme](#).

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